

STAGES OF IMITATION MODELING IN INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of the main features of ensuring competitiveness based on the study of the stages of simulation modeling in the innovative development of enterprises, and to the study of areas that serve to ensure the stability of enterprises and organizations in the market. The article studies the direct relationship between the innovation-based transformation of the economy and the innovative activities of the state, private business, state institutions and the scientific community. Therefore, the study of the essence and mechanism of innovative activity is an important stage for specialists. In the development of the enterprise, there is a need to develop the information environment, introduce new modules of the enterprise, modernize data processing and rapid response channels.

Keywords: imitation modeling, innovation stages, innovation, competition, sustainability, innovative activity, innovative potential.

Introduction The process of economic reforms being implemented in the region requires significant changes in the activities of enterprises and business entities, their adaptation to market requirements. In a market economy, accurate and scientifically based simulation modeling methods are of great importance in increasing competitiveness, efficient use of resources, and innovative development of enterprises. Therefore, simulation modeling of innovative development of enterprises is a necessary and relevant process in today's economic environment. With the help of this approach, regional business entities will be able to make decisions based on accurate analysis. Simulation modeling serves as an important tool for increasing the competitiveness of enterprises, ensuring financial stability, and identifying new directions for economic growth.

The main goal of research and practical approaches to the simulation of innovative development of enterprises is to ensure the financial stability of enterprises, increase economic efficiency and strengthen the competitiveness of the regional economy.

The concepts of innovative economic policy in enterprises are closely related to the concept of "regional development". V. N. Leksin and A. N. Shvetsov understand this as "such a mode of operation of the regional system, aimed at

the positive dynamics of the parameters of the standard of living and quality of life". "Reproduction of the social, economic, resource and ecological potential of a region with a stable, balanced population without mutual destruction"¹. At the same time, the concepts "territory" and "regional system" are perceived by them as synonyms. Under the territory, the authors mean a certain part of the social, natural, economic, infrastructural, cultural and historical or spatial entities of the state, which are under the control of local authorities.

We are close to such an approach in determining the essence of enterprise development. In this case, Regulation of regional development should be understood as a specially organized systematic local economic policy to ensure the stable and balanced functioning of territorial systems.

Note that budget risks in the formation of regional budget revenues as a result of economic instability have a significant impact on the flow of financial resources at the disposal of state bodies, the study of which can be concluded from this research analysis. Note that budget risks should be considered both as a possibility of loss and as an opportunity to gain.²

Our recommendation is that for the sustainable development of regional enterprises, it is necessary to introduce innovations, update technologies and management methods, effectively use resources, maximize the use of local raw materials, strengthen the institutional environment, develop a market economy, and attract investments.

The stages of innovative development of enterprises are carried out using various methods and analytical tools. In this assessment process, indicators are analyzed mainly at the following stages (Figure 1).

¹ Leksin V.N., Shvetsov A.N. Davlat va hududlar: hududiy rivojlanishni davlat tomonidan tartibga solish nazariyasi va amaliyoti. - M., 2007. S. 44.

² Rodger C., Petch J. Uncertainty and risk analysis : a practical guide from Business Dynamics. — UK: PrecewaterhouseCoopers, 1999. — 50 p.

Figure 1. Stages of innovative development of enterprise activities³

As we can see from the figure, the innovative development of regional enterprises is carried out in several stages. These stages include the processes of analyzing the current state of the enterprise, setting strategic goals, attracting investment, introducing innovations, and adapting to market conditions. Initial stage - Diagnostics and analysis - analyzes the current financial condition, assets, and liabilities of the enterprise. Financial stability and liquidity indicators are assessed. The structure of income and expenses is studied. The market segment and competitors are analyzed.

At the second stage, strategic planning develops a development strategy (growth, diversification or modernization). Plans for attracting capital and resources are determined. The long-term goals of the enterprise are determined. Directions for innovative and technological development are determined.

In investment and financing, sources of investment are determined (bank loans, state grants, private investors). Plans for effective capital allocation are developed. A strategy for attracting debt funds or issuing shares is developed. Opportunities for using state subsidies and benefits are studied.

The third stage of operational development and efficiency improvement involves optimizing production processes. Innovative technologies are introduced. Employee training programs are implemented. Measures are taken to reduce product costs and increase efficiency.

Strategies for expanding the market and increasing competitiveness are developed to enter new market segments. Marketing strategies are optimized. E-commerce and digital technologies are introduced. Opportunities for entering foreign markets and exporting are explored.

Monitoring and control involves constant monitoring of financial indicators and development processes. The internal audit system is strengthened. Development results are analyzed and necessary adjustments are made. Competitors' activities and market trends are monitored. This results in innovative development and sustainable growth. Management systems based on digital technologies and artificial intelligence are introduced. Development strategies based on the principles of environmental and social responsibility are implemented. Ways to create a sustainable financial system and implement long-term strategies are developed.

These stages are important for ensuring the sustainable development of regional enterprises and increasing their economic efficiency. Each stage requires a clear analysis and strategic approach..

In conclusion, simulation modeling is an important strategic tool for ensuring the innovative development of an enterprise. This approach allows complex business processes to be tested safely and under control, resources to be optimally allocated, and errors to be identified before they are implemented. The main benefit of simulation modeling is to make scientifically sound decisions, assess the effectiveness of innovations before they are implemented, and determine development paths based on different scenarios.

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